

EFFICIENCY OF MICROBIAL FUEL CELLS BASED ON THE SULPHATE-REDUCTION BY ETHANOL

Svetlana Bratkova¹, Zlatka Alexieva², Anatoliy Angelov¹, Katerina Nikolova¹, Petia Genova¹,
Rosen Ivanov¹, Maria Gerginova², Nadejda Peneva²

¹University of Mining and Geology "St. Ivan Rilski", 1700 Sofia; s_bratkova@mgu.bg

²Institute of Microbiology, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1113 Sofia

Corresponding author: Svetlana Bratkova, s_bratkova@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. The influence of hydraulic retention time (HRT) on the rate of sulphate-reduction and electricity generation of microbial fuel cell fed with ethanol was studied. The experiments were performed in the laboratory installation, consisting of an anaerobic fixed-bed reactor and a microbial fuel cell with air-cathode. An effective sulphate removal was achieved at hydraulic retention times 44 and 66 h. The effectiveness of COD removal raises with increasing the hydraulic retention time. The highest maximum power density of 258 mW/m² was obtained at 22 h HRT. The use of ethanol as an electron donor had a great impact on the composition of the microbial community. The metagenomic data obtained showed that the most abundant phylum in bacterial community was *Proteobacteria* – 87.8 %, and particularly *Gammaproteobacteria* – 53,1%. The sulphate reducing bacteria that can incompletely oxidise organic compounds usually with acetate as an end product were presented in the microbial community in anodic chamber. The dominant microbial species among sulphate reducing bacteria was *Desulfomicrobium mexicanus* (19,79%).

Keywords: Microbial fuel cell, Sulphate reduction, Microbial community, Metagenomic analyses, Wastewater treatment

Introduction

A computational analysis based on a citation network on fuel cells has shown that microbial fuel cells (MFCs) research is of great interest among scientists in recent years (Ogawa et al., 2018). The exponential increase in bioelectrochemical technology research indicates great advancements in this area of knowledge (Gul and Ahmad, 2019). The most significant use of MFCs is the electricity production during the wastewater treatment. In the last years, numerous studies on MFCs based on sulphate-reduction have been carried out (Gao et al., 2014; Miran et al., 2017; Gacitúa et al., 2018). This interest is related to the fact that a major environmental problem in the extraction and processing of mineral resources is the formation of wastewater, containing large concentrations of sulphate. MFCs based on sulphate-reduction have been used for Cu²⁺, Fe²⁺, Pb²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ removal (Miran et al., 2017; Peng et al., 2016) and metal recovery (Isosaari and Sillanpää, 2017). The technology has been applied also to organic carbon wastewater treatment (Lee et al., 2014), alcohol distillery wastewater treatment (Ha et al., 2012), diazo dye degradation (Miran et al., 2018).

In most MFCs studies, lactate was added as a carbon and energy source in synthetic wastewaters as it is a preferred electron donor for a large number of sulphate - reducing bacteria (SRB) (Miran et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2008; Gacitúa et al., 2018). The degree of sulphate's removal and chemical oxygen demand (COD) depends on a number of factors, the most important of which are pH, temperature, COD/SO₄²⁻ ratio, hydraulic retention time (HRT) (Kousi et al., 2011; Moon et al., 2015). When using lactate as a donor of electrons, during the sulphate reduction, the bacteria produce HCO₃⁻ ions resulting in increase of the pH of the medium. The extent of power density of MFCs based on the sulphate-reduction in conditions of lactate using has been in the range 180 – 680 mW/m² (Lee et al., 2012; Angelov et al., 2013; Gao et al., 2014; Miran et al., 2017). In studies on MFC with SRB consortia and glucose feed solution the amount of power density was much lower - from 9.33 to 39 mW/m² (Niyom et al., 2018; Bratkova et al., 2019). According to Chatterjee et al. (2017) MFC, fed with synthetic

wastewater with acetate and COD/sulphate ratio 2,5, could harvest power of 54,4 mW/m².

Few studies have been carried out on MFCs about the electricity production from ethanol (Kim et al., 2007; Song et al., 2005). According to Kim et al. (2007), the maximum power density of the two-chamber MFC was 40±2 mW/m². The same authors reported that when bacteria were transferred into a single-chamber MFC, the maximum power density increased to 488±12 mW/m². It should be noted that in these studies anaerobic sludge from a secondary anaerobic digester was used and the nutrient medium contained a mineral and vitamin solution in phosphate buffer (without sulphate) as well as that the cathode contained a Pt catalyst.

Despite scarce research with ethanol usage in MFCs, it is known that many SRB have the ability to use ethanol as an electron donor (Nagpal et al., 2000). Ethanol has been used as a source of carbon and energy to carry out sulphate-reduction in sulphidogenic bioreactors for mining wastewater treatment (Kaksonen et al., 2004; Bomberg et al., 2017). The stoichiometry of ethanol consumption can be represented by equation (1).

The effect of different electron donors on microbial community in MFCs was also a subject of many studies in the last years (Sun et al., 2010; Gezginici and Uysal, 2016). As the dominant group of bacterial consortia changed depending on the type of substrate, authors reported different predominant species in bacterial consortia in MFCs. It has been proven that the most common SRB found at the anode area, formed a biofilm in MFCs and fed with lactate belong to the genera *Desulfovibrio*, *Desulfomicrobium* and *Desulfobulbus* (Miran et al., 2017; Bratkova et al., 2019). It has also been found that SRB consortium reduced the sulphate with a higher rate than the individual single strains (Gacitúa et al. 2018).

The aim of this study was to investigate the performance of MFC and the taxonomic composition of the microbial community in the anodic area of MFCs when using ethanol as an electron donor. The effect of hydraulic retention time on the removal of sulphate and COD has also been studied.

Materials and methods

Design of the laboratory-scaled installation

In order to perform the planned laboratory experiment an installation was constructed, which is presented in Figure 1. The selected design of the laboratory installation consisted of a fixed-bed anaerobic bioreactor where the process of microbial dissimilative sulphate reduction and a MFC with an air-cathode were performed.

Fig. 1. A laboratory-scaled installation with integrated MFC based on the process of sulphate-reduction: 1 - feeding solution, 2 - peristaltic pump, 3 - anaerobic fixed-bed reactor, 4 - microbial fuel cell with an air-cathode, 5 - recirculation pump, 6 - hydrofoil and a sampling tank, 7 - collector, 8 - load resistance

The two chambers of the microbial fuel cell were separated with a proton exchange membrane type CMI-7000S (Membrane International Inc.) with an area of 0,0028 m². The two areas were with different volumes, as the anodic was of 0,50 dm³ and the cathodic one - 0,068 dm³. A carbon rod with a surface area of 0,0035 m² (diameter - 8 mm, length - 140 mm) was provided in the anodic chamber as an electrode. A 24 mm layer of pressed activated carbon with particles' fraction size of 2-4 mm was used in the air-cathode chamber. In this layer a graphite rod with a surface area of 0,001 m² (diameter - 8 mm, length -40 mm) was tucked in.

The anaerobic fixed-bed reactor had a volume of 0,33 dm³. The carrier for the biofilm was solution saturated natural zeolite - clinoptilolite, with a fraction size in the range of 2,5 to 5,0 mm. Its composition is given in a previous research (Angelov et al., 2013). For the saturation of 200 g zeolite 1L of the following solution was used: NH₄Cl - 10 g/l, K₂HPO₄ - 5g/l, MgSO₄·7H₂O - 4g/l. A recirculation pump (5) in an up-flow mode was devised for the homogenisation in the laboratory installation.

Initial cultivation of the consortium of sulphate-reducing bacteria

The anaerobic reactor was inoculated with a consortium of sulphate-reducing bacteria isolated from the fuel element. The culture medium contained 0,25 g/l K₂HPO₄, 0,5 g/l NH₄Cl, 2,0 g/l Na₂SO₄, 0,1 g/l CaCl₂, 4,0 g/l MgSO₄·7H₂O, 6,0 g/l, 6 ml/l ethanol 99%, 0,25 g/l yeast extract, as the pH was adjusted to 7,0. For a period of 2 months a sufficient adherence of the biofilm onto the saturated clinoptilolite in the bioreactor was achieved through a periodic replacement of about 70% of the liquid phase after reducing the sulphate concentration to 0,3 g/l with a fresh medium.

Process operation

The laboratory installation was fed continuously with the culture medium after the formation of the SRB biofilm. Different hydraulic retention times (of 13, 17, 22, 26, 33, 44 and 66 h) were maintained for a period of 4 months in order to study the influence of sulphates volume loading rate on the rate of the microbial processes. After reaching a dynamic equilibrium for each mode the effluents from laboratory-scaled installation were sampled repeatedly (3-5 times).

Microbial community analyses

Biomass sample from the anodic chamber of the MFC was taken 4 months after starting the experiment. Then the sample was centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatant was discarded. The residue obtained was stored at -80°C for further analysis.

Isolation and purification of genomic deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA)

The phenol/chloroform genomic DNA extraction was performed using standard methods (Maniatis et al., 1982). The purification of DNA was conducted with a GFX Genomic Blood DNA Purification Kit (Amersham Biosciences, Piscataway, NJ, USA).

Electrophoretic analyses

In the present study conventional agarose gel (0,7%) electrophoresis was used to separate the total genome DNA. The electrophoresis was run at a voltage varying from 50 to 100 V for approx. 1-2 hours. TBE buffer (0,04M Tris-HCl, 0,04M Boric acid H₃BO₃, 0,002M Ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid, pH 8,0) was applied after 10-fold dilution. The agarose gel with separated fragments DNA was stained with ethidium bromide solution. The fragments were visualised in Benchtop 3UV Transilluminator (UVP, LLC) under UV light ($\lambda = 254$ nm). A standard marker 50-3000bp DNA ladder (Sigma Aldrich) for DNA size-determination was used.

Metagenome analyses

After electrophoretic qualitative control, the probe isolated from the microbial biomass DNA and named MGU3 was quantified on Nanodrop. In the present experiment, the concentration of DNA from the MGU3 sample was 69, 98 ng/ μ l. The probe was processed to construct a library by the amplification of the V3-V4 region of 16S rRNA with specific primers in the laboratory of NGS Macrogen (South Korea). Libraries were sequenced on Illumina HiSeq platforms according to standard protocols. In the current experiments, the protocol included the target sequences with the V3 V4 primer pairs, which created a single amplicon of approximately 598 bp. The identified fragments for 16S RNA were subjected to bioinformatics OTU analysis and grouped into clusters.

Analytical methods

The overall sulphide concentrations were measured with Nanocolor test 1-88/05.09 immediately after the samples from the sampling tank were taken together with parameters as pH, Eh and electrical conductivity (EC). The sulphate contents were measured using a classic spectrophotometric method with BaCl₂. The usage of organic substrate was determined through the measuring of the chemical oxygen demand (COD) and the organic acids and alcohols were determined with a high-performance liquid chromatography. An Aminex HPX-87H

column from Bio-Rad coupled to a RI detector (LC-25RI) was used for HPLC; sulphuric acid (0,01 N) was used as an eluent.

The biofilm that was formed on the used zeolite and graphite in the anodic area after the operation of the installation for 4 months was measured through the Lowry method for protein quantitation.

Samples of the clinoptilolite and the graphite were monitored with a scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL/EO VERSION 1.0, and the selected samples were air-dried and gold-coated before the analysis.

The MFC was observed with a digital multimeter Keithley Model 175. A precise potentiometer with maximum value of 11 k Ω was used for the measurements of the external resistances, as during the measuring the external resistance was changed at stable output voltages. The times for reaching steady values of the current and the power were different depending on the external resistance. The geometric anodic surface area was taken into consideration when calculating the power and current densities.

Results and discussion

Removal of sulphate and COD and electricity generation in MFCs at different HRTs

Data about the basic chemical parameters of the effluents from laboratory installation at the tested HRTs are presented in Tables 1.

The pH values of the effluent from the laboratory installation at all HRTs tested were below 7. The pH of the effluent dropped most significantly at HRT of 66 h (Table 1). It is known that when ethanol is used as a source of carbon and energy, acetate and acidity (H^+) are initially produced (Bomberg et al., 2017). In the second step acetate may serve as an electron donor for SRB that completely oxidises organic compounds. Bicarbonate is produced, which leads to the increase of pH. From the observed changes in pH in the present study it could be assumed that incomplete oxidising sulphate-reducers, growing on ethanol, predominate in the microbial community.

Table 1. General parameters measured at the outlets of the laboratory installation

Parameter	Feed solution	Effluent at different HRT, h						
		13	17	22	26	33	44	66
pH	7 \pm 0,10	6,38 \pm 0,09	6,35 \pm 0,12	6,32 \pm 0,11	6,33 \pm 0,13	6,27 \pm 0,10	6,15 \pm 0,13	6,05 \pm 0,12
Eh, mV	-	-332 \pm 12	-380 \pm 14	-388 \pm 10	-369 \pm 12	-351 \pm 18	-348 \pm 13	-332 \pm 16
EC, mS/cm	6,68 \pm 0,02	7,58 \pm 0,08	7,56 \pm 0,10	7,46 \pm 0,04	7,54 \pm 0,03	7,19 \pm 0,05	7,1 \pm 0,06	7,07 \pm 0,03
SO ₄ ²⁻ , g/l	3,0 \pm 0,05	1,21 \pm 0,06	1,02 \pm 0,04	0,92 \pm 0,12	0,85 \pm 0,08	0,69 \pm 0,05	0,37 \pm 0,04	0,063 \pm 0,02
S ²⁻ , mg/l	-	177,3 \pm 23	227,74 \pm 0,1	330,81 \pm 20	241,84 \pm 19	213,6 \pm 21	203,29 \pm 19	204,43 \pm 22
COD, mg/l	9755 \pm 25	5913 \pm 15	4780 \pm 20	4100 \pm 30	3690 \pm 25	3280 \pm 10	2950 \pm 15	2455 \pm 20

Table 2. Sulphate and COD volume loading rates, sulphate and COD removal in the laboratory installation

HRT, h	Sulphate volume loading rate, g/l.h	Rate of sulphate-reduction, mg/l.h	Sulphate removal, %	COD volume loading rate, g/l.h	COD removal, %
13	0,231	138	59,7	0,750	39,4
17	0,176	116	66,0	0,574	50,1
22	0,136	95	69,3	0,443	58,0
26	0,115	83	71,7	0,352	62,2
33	0,091	70	77,0	0,296	66,4
44	0,068	60	87,7	0,222	69,8
66	0,045	45	97,9	0,149	74,8

Due to the lower pH values, most of the microbial generated hydrogen sulphide was in the form of fully protonated H₂S, a component of gas phase. The concentration of S²⁻ at the outlet of the laboratory installation was determined between 177 and 330 mg/l. The undissociated H₂S is toxic to SRB and the rate of sulphate-reduction and the specific growth rate of SRB correlate inversely to its concentration (Moosa and Harrison, 2006).

COD/sulphate ratio and HRT are the two most important factors for sulphate removal and bioelectricity generation (Zhang et al. 2012). The calculated COD/SO₄²⁻ ratio was around 3,25. Data for the rate of sulphate-reduction and sulphate and COD removal are presented in Table 2. We observed that the decrease of HRT from 66 to 13 h led to an increase of the rate of the sulphate-reduction, as the dependence is described by the following equation:

$$\text{Rate of sulf.-red., (mg/l.h)} = 808,67 \times \text{HRT}^{-0,6919} \quad (R^2 = 0,9977), \quad (2)$$

The maximum sulphate removal (97,9 %) and COD removal (74,8%) were established at a HRT of 66 h. The measured COD values of the outflow were high because of the incomplete oxidation of organic compounds. Data from HPLC analyses showed the incomplete oxidation of ethanol to acetate, as the acetate concentration in the effluent were of 0,53, 0,78 and 1,25 g/l at HRTs 13, 33 and 66 h, respectively.

The open circuit voltage (OCV) values for the MFC at different HRTs were in the range 658 – 756 mV. The polarisation and power density curves for the studied MFC are shown on Fig. 2 and 3.

Fig 2. Cell voltage in the MFCs as a function of current density at different HRT

The highest maximum power density of 258 mW/m² was obtained at hydraulic retention time of 22 h. At the same HRT the highest concentration of hydrogen sulphide (330 mg/l) was measured. The results obtained are consistent with those reported by other authors which proves that the current produced by the electrodes was dependent on the concentration of the sulphide (Zhao et al., 2008).

Fig 3. Power output density in the MFCs as a function of current density at different HRT

The biofilms formed on the zeolite and the graphite were studied after 4 months of operation by protein determination. Biomass attached on the anodic surface was 0,98 mg protein/cm². The quantification of the microbial biofilms on zeolite was 8,78 mg protein/cm³. The yields of protein, extracted from the biomass on the anodic surface of MFC and zeolite were considerably lower in comparison to growth on glucose and lactate (Bratkova et al., 2019).

The morphology of the biofilms attached on the zeolite and the graphite electrode were analysed through SEM. The biofilms were complex structures of aggregated microbial cells within a matrix of extracellular polymeric substances (Fig.4).

Fig. 4. SEM images of the SRB consortium biofilms on zeolite and graphite (x 6 000) after 4 months; a thin gold layer applied after drying of samples to ensure conductivity. a) Zeolite with biofilm; b) Graphite anode with biofilm

Microbial community results

The population structure and phylogenetic diversity of bacterial community cultured in the anodic area of MFC were studied by metagenomic analysis. The main purpose was to identify the bacterial groups participating in the process of sulphate reduction with the use of ethanol as a source of carbon and energy.

A bioinformatics analysis of the metagenomic data showed that Archaea was virtually absent (0,01%). The identified microorganisms in the studied consortia constitute up to 99,50% and the unidentified microorganisms are a small part - 0,49%. *Proteobacteria* have the largest part among the identified bacteria - 87,79%, as representatives of *Gammaproteobacteria* are the predominant, followed by *Deltaproteobacteria* and *Epsilonproteobacteria* (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Distribution of the classes of proteobacteria in the studied microbial community

Most of the *Gammaproteobacteria* identified in the studied microbial community belonged to the order *Pseudomonadales*. *Deltaproteobacteria* include a large number of those known for their ability to reduce sulphur and sulphate bacteria, such as the representatives of genera *Desulfuromonas*, *Desulfovibrio*, *Desulfobacter*, *Desulfococcus*, *Desulfoboche*, etc.

The results show that the most significant part of all identified microorganisms in the studied community belongs to the genera *Pseudomonas* (46,89%) and *Desulfovibrio* (20,86%). The most common species of the genus *Pseudomonas* was *P. veronii* - 43,71%, and of the genus *Desulfovibrio* – *D. mexicanus* - 19,79%.

The percentage of sulphate-reducing bacteria was 23,09%, and the total bacteria involved or having a direct effect on sulphate reduction was 32%. The distribution of the species of sulphate-reducing bacteria in the studied microbial community with included carbon source ethanol is shown in Fig.6.

Fig. 6. Distribution of the species of sulphate-reducing bacteria

Desulfovibrio mexicanus is a mesophilic, anaerobic, aerotolerant gram-negative bacterium that reduces sulphate with optimal growth at 37° C and pH 7,2 in a medium containing lactate. It uses also pyruvate, formate, casamino acids, serine, cysteine, H₂ and ethanol as electron donors in the presence of thiosulphate as electron acceptor. Sulphate, elemental sulphur and sulphite also serve as electron acceptors, but not nitrates or fumarate.

Microorganisms, able to reduce elemental sulphur belonging to the genus *Sulfurospirillum*, organohalide respiratory Epsilonproteobacteria, were found in the studied microbial community. The range of growth substrates includes many toxic compounds, which allows many species of *Sulfurospirillum* (eg *Sulfurospirillum arsenophilum*, *Sulfurospirillum cavolei*) to thrive in contaminated habitats (Goris T. and Diekert G., 2016). In microaerophilic conditions a number of species of the genus *Sulfurospirillum* could use acetate as a source of carbon and fumarate, pyruvate, lactate, malate, succinate, hydrogen and format as electron donors. The largest presence was registered for the species sulphur-reducing bacteria *S. cavolei* (4,75%) and *S. arsenophilum* (4,45%).

The taxonomic diversity of microbial consortia within MFCs changed depending on the type of donor of electrons (Gezginci and Uysal, 2016). The results obtained in our previous studies of microbial communities isolated from the same sulphidogenic bioreactor are comparable, but when using glucose (MGU1) or lactate (MGU2) as a carbon source (Bratkova et al., 2019) will demonstrate significant differences in taxonomic diversity. For instance, the lowest percentage of SRB was detected in the case of cultivation with glucose (3,18%) where *D. mexicanus* (2,73%) was predominant species. The variety of sulphate reducers is greater when using lactate as an electron donor. The presence of seven such species was detected in anodic area of MFC with a lactate feed solution. They constitute 4,49% of the microorganisms identified in the test sample. Five types of sulphate reducing bacteria have been identified in MGU3, but their total number in the microbial community is more significant (21,46%) and the main part of it is due to *D. mexicanus*.

Conclusions

In this study, effective sulphate and COD removal with parallel electricity generation were achieved at hydraulic retention times 44 and 66 h by the laboratory installation consisting of an anaerobic fixed-bed reactor and a microbial fuel cell with ethanol as a source of carbon and energy. The highest maximum power density of 258 mW/m² was obtained at hydraulic retention time of 22 h. The anode potential was controlled mainly by the concentration of sulphide. Data received from metagenomic analysis showed that sulphate-reducing and sulphur-reducing bacteria were involved in the transformation of sulphur compounds. The microbial community in anodic chamber contains significant amount SRB that oxidise the organic compounds incompletely with acetate as an end product. The dominant microbial species was identified as *Desulfovibrio mexicanus* - 19,79%.

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References

- Angelov, A., Bratkova, S., Loukanov, A., 2013. Microbial fuel cell based on electroactive sulphate-reducing biofilm. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 67, 283–286.
- Bomberg, M., Mäkinen, J., Salo, M., Arnold, M., 2017. Microbial Community Structure and Functions in Ethanol-Fed Sulphate Removal Bioreactors for Treatment of Mine Water, *Microorganisms*, 5, 61.
- Bratkova, S., Alexieva, Z., Angelov, A., Nikolova, K., Genova, P., Ivanov, R., Gerginova, M., Peneva, N., Beschkov, V., 2019. Efficiency of microbial fuel cells based on the sulphate reduction by lactate and glucose. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 16(10), 6145–6156.
- Chatterjee, P., Ghangrekar, M.M., Rao, S., Kumar, S., 2017. Biotic conversion of sulphate to sulphide and abiotic conversion of sulphide to sulphur in a microbial fuel cell using cobalt oxide octahedrons as cathode catalyst. *Bioprocess Biosyst Eng.* 40(5), 759–768.
- Gacitúa, M.A., Muñoz, E., González, B., 2018. Bioelectrochemical sulphate reduction on batch reactors: Effect of inoculum-type and applied potential on sulphate consumption and pH. *Bioelectrochemistry*, 119, 26–32.
- Gao, C., Wang, A., Zhao, Y., 2014. Contribution of sulphate-reducing bacteria to the electricity generation in microbial fuel cells. *Advanced Materials Research*, 1008-1009, 285–289.
- Gezginci, M., Uysal, Y., 2016. The Effect of Different Substrate Sources Used in Microbial Fuel Cells on Microbial Community. *JSM Environ Sci Ecol*, 4(3), 1035 p.
- Goris, T., Diekert, G., 2016. The Genus *Sulfurospirillum*. In: Adrian L., Löffler F. (eds) *Organohalide-Respiring Bacteria*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Gul, M.M., Ahmad, K.S., 2019. Bioelectrochemical systems: Sustainable bio-energy powerhouses, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 142, 111576, doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2019.111576
- Ha, P.T., Lee, T.K., Rittmann, B.E., Park, J., Chang, I.S., 2012. Treatment of Alcohol Distillery Wastewater Using a Bacteroidetes-Dominant Thermophilic Microbial Fuel Cell, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 46(5), 3022–3030. doi.org/10.1021/es203861v.
- Isosaari, P., Sillanpää, M. 2017. Use of sulphate reducing bioreactors and bioelectrochemical reactors for metal recovery from mine water, *Separation & Purification Reviews, Separation & Purification Reviews*, 46(1), 1–20.
- Kaksonen, A., Franzmann, P., Puhakka, J., 2004. Effects of hydraulic retention time and sulphide toxicity on ethanol and acetate oxidation in sulphate-reducing metal-precipitating fluidized-bed reactor, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 86, 332–343.
- Kim, J.R., Jung, S.H., Regan, J.M., Logan, B.E., 2007. Electricity generation and microbial community analysis of alcohol powered microbial fuel cells, *Bioresource Technology*, 98, 2568–2577.
- Kousi, P., Remoundaki, E., Hatzikioseyan, A., Tsezos, M., 2011. Sulphate-reducing fixed-bed bioreactors fed with different organic substrates for metal precipitation. *Biohydrometallurgy: Biotech key to unlock mineral resources value*, 18-22 September 2011, China.
- Lee, D., Lee, C., Chang, J., 2012. Treatment and electricity harvesting from sulphate/sulfide-containing wastewaters

- using microbial fuel cell with enriched sulphate-reducing mixed culture. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 243, 67–72.
- Lee, D., Liu, X., Weng, H., 2014. Sulphate and organic carbon removal by microbial fuel cell with sulphate-reducing bacteria and sulphide-oxidising bacteria anodic biofilm. *Bioresource Technology*, 156, 14–19.
- Maniatis, T., Fritch, E.F., Sambrook, J., 1982. *Molecular cloning: A laboratory manual*. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, NY.
- Miran, W., Jang, J., Nawaz, M., Shahzad, A., Jeong, S.E., Jeon, C.O., Lee, D.S., 2017. Mixed sulphate-reducing bacteria-enriched microbial fuel cells for the treatment of wastewater containing copper, *Chemosphere*, 189, 134–142.
- Miran, W., Jang, J., Nawaz, M., Shahzad, A., Lee, D.S., 2018. Sulphate-reducing mixed communities with the ability to generate bioelectricity and degrade textile diazo dye in microbial fuel cells, *Journal of Hazardous Materials Jun 15*, 352, 70–79. doi: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2018.03.027.
- Moon, C., Singh, R., Veeravalli, S.S., Shanmugam, S.R., Chaganti, S.R., Lalman, J.A., Heath, D.D., 2015. Effect of COD:SO₄²⁻ Ratio, HRT and Linoleic Acid Concentration on Mesophilic Sulphate Reduction: Reactor Performance and Microbial Population Dynamics. *Water*, 7, 2275–2292.
- Moosa, S., Harrison, S.T.L., 2006. Product inhibition by sulphide species on biological sulphate reduction for the treatment of acid mine drainage. *Hydrometallurgy*, 83, 214–222.
- Nagpal, S., Chuichulcherm, S., Livingston, A., Peeva, L., 2000. Ethanol Utilization by Sulphate-Reducing Bacteria: An Experimental and Modelling Study, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 70, 533–543.
- Niyom, W., Komolyothin, D., Suwannasilp, B.B., 2018. Important Role of Abiotic Sulfide Oxidation in Microbial Fuel Cells Treating High-Sulphate Wastewater, *Engineering journal*, 22(4).
- Ogawa, T., Takeuchi, M., Kajikawa, Y. 2018. Comprehensive Analysis of Trends and Emerging Technologies in All Types of Fuel Cells Based on a Computational Method. *Sustainability* 10, 458, doi:10.3390/su10020458.
- Peng, X., Tang, T., Zhu, X., Jia, G., Ding, Y., Chen, Y., Yang, Y., Tang, W., 2016. Remediation of acid mine drainage using microbial fuel cell based on sludge anaerobic fermentation, *Environmental Technology*, DOI:10.1080/09593330.2016.1262462.
- Song, S.Q., Zhou, W.J., Zhou, Z.H., Jiang, L.H., Sun, G.Q., Xin, Q., Leontidis, V., Kontou, S., Tsiakaras, P., 2005. Direct ethanol PEM fuel cells: The case of platinum-based anodes, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 30, 995–1001.
- Sun, M., Tong, Z., Sheng, G., Chen, Y., Zhang, F., Mu, Z., Wang, H., Zeng, R.J., Liu, X., Yu, H., Wei, L., Ma, F., 2010. Microbial communities involved in electricity generation from sulphide oxidation in a microbial fuel cell, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 26, 470–476.
- Zhang, B., Zhang, J., Yang, Q., Feng, C., Zhu, Y., Ye, Z., Ni, J., 2012. Investigation and optimization of the novel UASB–MFC integrated system for sulphate removal and bioelectricity generation using the response surface methodology (RSM). *Bioresource Technology*, 124, 1–7.
- Zhao, F., Rahunen, N., Varcoe, J.R., Chandra, A., Avignone-Rossa, C., Thumser, A.E., Slade, R.C.T., 2008. Activated carbon cloth as anode for sulphate removal in a microbial fuel cell. *Environ Sci Technol*, 42, 4971–4976.